

Supplementary Materials: Dual Reference Genomes from F1 Hybrids: Phased Assembly of North African Catfish and Bighead Catfish with Hi-C Data

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ABSTRACT

Supplementary Methods and Additional Results

Supplementary Methods

Benchmarking Methodology

This section presents the validation methodology used to assess genome assembly quality and completeness. Metrics of continuity, structural accuracy, base accuracy, and functional completeness were employed following the Vertebrate Genome Project (VGP) standards¹.

Continuity and Summary Statistics

Continuity and summary statistics were assessed using scaffold/contig metrics (N50, N90, NG50, LG50, and LG90) calculated with RagTag v2.1.0² using the command `ragtag.py asmstats -g`.

Repeat Completeness and Continuity

Repeat completeness was measured by estimating the percentage of fully assembled LTR retroelements (LTR-RTs) and computing the Long Terminal Repeat Assembly Index (LAI) using LTR_retriever v2.9.00³ and LAI⁴. Complex repeat assessment (centromeres) was performed using TandemTools and TandemQUAST v1⁵. Telomere presence, absence, and orientation were predicted using TIDK implemented in TeloExplorer (`-m 50 -c animal`), a module of QuarTeT⁶. Gap estimation was performed using the detgaps script (available at <https://github.com/dfguan/asset>).

Structural Accuracy Assessment

Structural accuracy was evaluated using CRAQ v1.0.9⁷ with parameters `sms_coverage=5 ngs_coverage=20 -B T -minimap2-sensitive -q 20 -m 2 -f 0.4 -h 0.6 -r 0.75 -a 20`. CRAQ evaluates assembly quality based on clipped-read evidence from both short and long reads, reporting:

- **Clip-based Regional Errors (CREs):** Small-scale local misassemblies identified by short-read clipping
- **Clip-based Structural Errors (CSEs):** Large-scale misassemblies supported by long-read clipping
- **R-AQI and S-AQI scores:** Based on CREs and CSEs respectively
- **Assembly Quality Index (AQI):** Global score (0-100) where higher values indicate better assembly integrity

Results were visualized using the Integrative Genome Viewer (IGV)⁸.

Cross-Species Structural Correctness

Cross-species structural validation was performed using MashMap2 v3.1.3⁹ for one-to-one nucleotide-level alignments of orthologous segments with parameters `-s 2000000 -pi 90 -c 100000`.

Base Accuracy and Assembly Completeness

Base accuracy was assessed using Merqury v1.3¹⁰ to calculate quality values (QV) and 21-mer genome completeness. Merqury was run with three different k-mer databases: Illumina-only, HiFi-only, and hybrid databases combining Illumina and HiFi reads. Functional completeness was evaluated using BUSCO v5.6.1¹¹ with the Actinopterygii lineage dataset (-l actinopterygii_odb10).

Nucleotide accuracy was verified through read-to-assembly mapping using:

- **HiFi reads:** minimap2 (-ax map-hifi -secondary=no) and Winnowmap (-W repetitive.15.txt) at MAPQ >10
- **ONT reads:** minimap2 (-ax map-ont) and Winnowmap (-ax map-pb) at MAPQ >10

Visualizations were performed using IGV with genome files and Merqury k-mer tracks.

Sample Collection and DNA Extraction

A one-year-old adult female hybrid catfish (*Clarias macrocephalus* × *Clarias gariepinus*) was obtained from the Faculty of Fisheries at Kasetsart University, Bangkok, Thailand. The F1 specimen was the offspring of a cross between a female F0 bighead catfish parent and a male F0 North African catfish parent. Sex determination was performed through external gonadal morphology examination and histological analysis following established protocols^{12,13}. Genomic DNA was extracted from liver tissue using a salting-out protocol¹⁴.

Sequencing Strategy and Platform Details

The sequencing strategy employed four complementary sequencing technologies, each selected for specific advantages in hybrid genome assembly:

PacBio HiFi Long-read Sequencing

PacBio HiFi sequencing was performed on a Sequel II system using SMRT cell technology. This platform was selected for maximizing genome assembly quality with base accuracy >99.9%¹⁵. The sequencing generated 10.62 Gb of raw data, corresponding to approximately 12.9× genome coverage (6-7× per haplotype). Key metrics included:

- Read length N50: 10,379 bp
- Mean quality score: Q28.7
- Median quality score: Q36
- Reads >Q30: 72%
- Reads >Q25: 86%
- High-quality reads (>Q10): 191,790 reads totaling 5.07 Gb

Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) Long-read Sequencing

ONT sequencing was used to increase assembly continuity and span complex repetitive genomic regions¹⁶. Libraries were prepared from 1D-fragmented and size-selected DNA fragments that were end-polished, nick-repaired, and A-tailed before adapter ligation. DNA quality was assessed using QuBit prior to sequencing on the MiniION system (NovoGene). Key metrics included:

- Total raw data: 32.62 Gb
- Genome coverage: 36× (18× per haplotype)
- Read N50: 4 kb
- Median quality: Q11
- Reads >Q7: 97.0% (4,023,582 reads)
- Base error rate: 20%
- Usable coverage after quality filtering: <4×

Note: The ONT data quality was lower than expected, resulting in only a small fraction being suitable for assembly purposes.

Illumina Paired-End Short-read Sequencing

Standard Illumina paired-end sequencing was performed on the NextSeq2000 platform (NovoGene) for assembly polishing, genome size estimation, heterozygosity assessment, and post-assembly validation¹⁷. Sequencing parameters:

- Platform: Illumina NextSeq2000
- Read length: 151 nucleotides (paired-end)
- Total raw data: 50 Gb
- Genome coverage: 36×
- Mean quality: Q25
- Reads Q30+: 92%

Proximity Ligation (Hi-C) Sequencing

Hi-C sequencing provided long-range chromatin interaction data essential for haplotype phasing and chromosome-scale scaffolding^{18,19}. The protocol followed standard in situ Hi-C methodology:

Library Preparation:

1. Chromatin cross-linking was performed in nuclei
2. Restriction digestion using DpnII endonuclease
3. Chromatin conformation capture library preparation by Phase Genomics
4. Sequencing on Illumina NextSeq2000 platform

Sequencing Metrics:

- Read length: 151 bp paired-end
- Total raw data: 37.19 Gb
- Genome coverage: 40×
- Reads Q30+: 97.18%
- Read pairs per billion genome bases: 100M

Hi-C Contact Analysis:

- **Haplotype 1:** 123.96M read pairs sequenced
 - Unique Hi-C contacts: 74.77M
 - Valid contacts: 59.40M (22.71M inter-chromosomal, 36.69M intra-chromosomal)
 - Short-range contacts (<20 kb): 17.47M
 - Long-range contacts (>20 kb): 19.72M
- **Haplotype 2:** Similar metrics to Haplotype 1

Raw Data Processing and Quality Control

Quality Assessment

Raw sequencing data quality was evaluated using:

- FastQC v0.1.12 for short reads (<http://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc/>)
- NanoPlot v1.42.0 for long reads²⁰

Adapter Trimming and Preprocessing

- **Illumina reads:** Trimmed for synthetic adapters using AdapterRemoval v2.3.3²¹
- **PacBio HiFi reads:** Processed with HiFiAdapterFilt v64d1c7b using parameters:

```
-reward 1 -penalty -5 -gapopen 3 -gapextend 3 -dust no  
-soft_masking true -evaluate 700 -searchsp 1750000000000
```

- **Hi-C reads:** No adapter trimming performed to preserve ligation junction information

Contamination Screening

Contamination assessment was performed using Mash v2.3²² against the RefSeq database:

- Database: refseq.genomes + plasmids.k21.s1000.msh
- Parameters: sketch size=1000, k=21

Genome Survey and K-mer Analysis

K-mer Distribution Analysis

Canonical k-mer distributions were calculated for genome size estimation and heterozygosity assessment:

- **Tools:** Meryl¹⁰, Jellyfish v2.3.1²³
- **K-mer sizes:** 21-mer and 31-mer
- **Input data:** Trimmed Illumina and HiFi reads
- **Analysis software:** K-mer Analysis Toolkit (KAT) v2.4.1²⁴, GenomeScope v2.0²⁵

Genome Size and Heterozygosity Estimates

GenomeScope 2.0 analysis revealed:

- **Haploid genome size (k=21):** 1.8 Gb
- **Haploid genome size (k=31):** 910 Mb
- **Heterozygosity (k=21):** 10%
- **Heterozygosity (k=31):** 0.549%

The difference in estimates between k=21 and k=31 reflects the hybrid nature of the genome, where smaller k-mers capture inter-species divergence (10%), while larger k-mers primarily detect intra-species polymorphisms (0.54%). The expected hybrid genome size was determined to be approximately 1.8 Gb, representing the combined genomic information from both parental species.

Assembly Pipeline and Filtering

Contig and Scaffold Filtering

Quality filtering was performed using Seqkit v2.7.0²⁶:

- **Size filtering:** `-by-length -reverse -m 2,500,000`
- **Scaffold removal:** Sequences <15,000 bp excluded
- **Pattern extraction:** `seqkit grep -n -r -p "$pattern" $genome.fa`

Supplementary Results

Expected Genome Sizes, K-mer Profiles and Hybrid Genome Assessment

Figure 2 presents GenomeScope2.0 k-mer profiles to evaluate genome size, heterozygosity, and repeat content for the F1 hybrid genome and its parental species. Separate k-mer distributions are shown for individual parental lineages from distinct bloodlines to assess intra-species variation.

- **Parental individuals (same species, different bloodlines):** The *C. macrocephalus* individual exhibits low heterozygosity (0.056%), while *C. gariepinus* shows moderate heterozygosity (1.56%), consistent with expected intraspecific levels. Broader peaks at k=21 likely reflect lower Illumina coverage (<20×), but species-level divergence remains evident.
- **F1 hybrid genome:** At k=21, the estimated genome size is approximately 1.8 Gb, aligning with the combined haploid contributions of both species. The apparent heterozygosity rate of 10% reflects typical divergence in interspecific F1 hybrids with distinct subgenomes. This divergence results in a bimodal distribution due to haplotype differences. At k=31, heterozygosity estimates in the F1 hybrid decrease as k-mer size increases, reflecting partial subgenome separation and reducing false overlaps.

Assembly Architecture Validation

Our haplotype-resolved assembly successfully generated 55 Hi-C scaffolds corresponding to the expected karyotype of F1 hybrid catfish, comprising 27 pseudochromosomes for *C. macrocephalus* and 28 for *C. gariepinus*. This chromosome count is consistent with previous karyotype studies of bighead catfish, North African catfish, and their F1 offspring^{?,27}.

Hi-C Contact Matrix Validation

Individual Hi-C contact matrices were generated for each chromosome-scale scaffold to confirm subgenome identity and structural integrity. The analysis revealed distinct, internally consistent chromosomal contact patterns supporting successful haplotype separation and chromosome-scale phasing.

North African Catfish Subgenome (28 chromosomes)

The Hi-C interaction maps (Figure 5) demonstrate:

- Strong diagonal contact patterns without major off-diagonal disruptions
- High contiguity with minimal mis-assemblies
- Minor local noise in some chromosomes, addressed through manual curation
- Clear chromosome boundaries supporting accurate scaffold assignment

Bighead Catfish Subgenome (27 chromosomes)

Similarly, the bighead catfish subgenome Hi-C maps (Figure 6) show:

- Well-defined diagonal patterns consistent with chromosome-length assemblies
- High-quality contact matrices with minimal structural noise
- Some chromosomes (Chr07, Chr23) required manual correction for off-diagonal signals
- Successful resolution of chromosome-scale structure

The visual clarity and signal symmetry of both Hi-C map sets confirm successful subgenome resolution and faithful representation of the diploid karyotype ($2n = 55$) in the F1 hybrid assembly.

Assembly Review and Manual Curation

Iterative Polishing of the Hybrid Catfish Genome

Over the course of this study, more than half a year was dedicated to manual genome assembly curation, with significant time spent reviewing alignments using IGV. The curated assembly exhibits almost no remaining conflicts with raw data and contains no known mis-joins. This effort was essential to overcome limitations of variant callers, which often struggle to distinguish true variations from allelic differences—even when using correction tools such as Merqury¹⁰ or Merfin²⁸.

Although both subgenomes in the F1 hybrid were assembled using the same pipeline, the bighead catfish subgenome showed slightly lower nucleotide quality, likely due to local repeat complexity. This reflects commonly observed assembly

challenges in teleost fishes. Heterozygosity analyses based on pure-blooded, non-F1 individuals indicate that *C. macrocephalus* has a lower heterozygosity rate (approximately 0.62%) compared to *C. gariepinus* (approximately 1.0%). The current assembly achieved high QV scores (both at k=21 and k=31) and demonstrated robust completeness metrics, including CRAQ structural accuracy. Manual curation, iterative polishing, and uniform read coverage were key to overcoming the inherent limitations of software and sequencing depth. The final output includes 55 pseudochromosomes, accurately capturing both parental haplotypes from the single F1 individual.

For the initial assembly phase, the most effective strategy was to generate multiple assemblies from the same dataset and merge or scaffold them post hoc. For example, combining outputs from Flye and GreenHill with Hifiasm improved the resolution of complex genomic regions. Under very low read-depth conditions, Hifiasm sometimes extended a read and switched to a longer overlapping read—even when these reads differed by more than 20 SNPs—a level of mismatch unlikely to stem from sequencing error alone. Furthermore, caution is advised against using related reference genomes to fill missing segments unless each insertion is manually validated, as errors can outnumber correct placements in such cases. For Hi-C scaffolds, at least three rounds of manual review using Juicebox were conducted, which involved splitting contigs at off-diagonal signals and identifying new scaffold gaps. This highly challenging step yielded substantial improvements, reducing the number of contigs from over 2,000 to fewer than 500.

Manual Assembly Curation and Telomeric Refinement

Successful telomeric refinement was another major achievement. Manual extension of clipped sequences aligned to chromosomes introduced at least five new telomeric sequences with canonical [TTAGGG]_n motifs. While telomeres are not biologically critical for most genome analyses, their identification enables accurate delineation of chromosome ends. For example, the left telomeric repeat count of *C. gariepinus* chromosome 16 increased from n=138 to n=1,602, and chromosome 18 from n=268 to n=1,411. In *C. macrocephalus*, the left telomere of chromosome 7 increased from n=199 to n=924 repeats. These updates raised the number of pseudochromosomes with telomeres on both ends from 43 to 48, while chromosomes with only one telomere decreased from 8 to 7. In total, telomeric additions contributed approximately 400 kb to the assembly, marking critical progress toward telomere-to-telomere (T2T) continuity for multiple chromosomes.

Beyond telomeres, a subgenomic analysis highlighted additional differences between the parental haplotypes. These include varying heterozygosity rates and assembly complexities due to low nanopore coverage. While most genomic gaps have been filled, the quality of centromeric and satellite regions remains uncertain. In particular, regions lacking HiFi read coverage or covered only by MAPQ0 Illumina reads continue to rely on low-accuracy ONT data, posing challenges for reaching base-level accuracy in these zones.

Manual and Automated QV Polishing

For QV polishing, automatic QV correction was effectively complemented by manual curation. Clair3 initially identified over 60,000 variants, which were subsequently resolved and corrected using Merfin. Despite reaching a quality value of QV60 at k=21, a final round of manual curation introduced 8,410 edits, including 551 large structural variants, resulting in a QV increase of 1-5 points. More than four rounds of manual curation (guided by IGV) were completed:

- **First round:** Sniffles2 identified 755 target regions across all alignment files.
- **Second round:** Cross-assembly curation using Unimap, manually curating scaffolds generated by Flye, GreenHill, and P contigs from Hifiasm, incorporating seqmer error files. This led to 2,221 manual edits and the application of 5,951 variants to the polished genome.
- **Third round:** Utilizing Winnowmap and Unimap, manual identification of 8,710 variants from 5,740 alignments, of which 1,932 were applied to the assembly. This step also resolved 300 gaps following Sniffles2 and BCFtools consensus-based corrections.
- **Fourth round:** Correction of 97 large structural variants, including 10 that were only visible through VerityMap alignments. Although QV60 was reached without masking, 65 new gaps were introduced to mask sequences lacking correct read support or showing high QV error profiles, ensuring the exclusion of low-confidence regions.

After masking, 247 structural variants (196 insertions and 73 deletions) were identified using Sniffles2 and applied to the genome. These were derived from ONT pb-falconc-filtered alignments realigned at the boundaries of self-realigned Hifiasm contigs with a 50 nt margin. Approximately 90% were homozygous and 10% heterozygous, and these edits contribute to contig

linkage after QV60 polishing.

At this stage, genomic error k-mers were not uniformly distributed along chromosomes, suggesting error clustering. These were often found in ONT-only or 1-depth read coverage regions (total N=511 loci). Using Clair3²⁹, 22,625 ONT-based consensus errors and 7,558 variants from HiFi Winnowmap alignments were further corrected, increasing the QV to a median quality value at k=31.

To illustrate the process of manual curation and validate the hybrid genome assembly, IGV was used to inspect quality improvements and structural issues (Figure 3). In Chromosome 03, a clear reduction in k-mer error rates and an increase in QV after polishing was observed. Note that QV50 and QV60 are not directly comparable across different k-mer sizes: k=31 is more sensitive but prone to false positives, while k=21 is more specific but may miss true errors. Chromosome 02 revealed a false duplication event present in Hifiasm but not in Flye, confirmed by doubled homozygous coverage and lack of high-quality HiFi alignments. A single ONT read spanned the duplicated region and a clipped Illumina read supported boundary precision.

Following eight months of manual genome curation, the estimated QV was raised from Q40 to Q60. These results demonstrate that an F1 hybrid genome can surpass the nucleotide-level accuracy of a single-species genome. For example, the separate assembly of pure-breed bighead catfish reached a median QV of Q40-Q50 (k=21, k=31, pileup), while the current F1 genome is ten times more accurate using similar sequencing coverage, tools, and time investment.

Comparative Genomics Preparation

Gene annotations (exons/coding sequences) were transferred from *C. gariepinus* (GCA_024256425.1) to both catfish subgenomes using Liftoff³⁰ with 85% coverage-identity threshold. Orthologous gene clusters (Orthogroups) were identified using OrthoFinder v2.5.5² with parameters `orthofinder -f /proteomes -M msa -a 126 -t 126`. Subsequently, rbhXpress and macrosyntR v0.2.19³¹ were utilized to analyze the resulting orthogroups and visualize their syntenic relationships across species.

Supplementary Figures

Data Availability

Genome Assembly Records

F1 Hybrid Catfish Assembly (isolate: CGAF)

- **Bighead catfish subgenome** (TaxID: 35657): GenBank accession JBLWFY000000000.1
- **North African catfish subgenome** (TaxID: 13013): GenBank accession JBLWFZ000000000.1
- **NCBI BioProject**: PRJNA1153495
- **F1 hybrid catfish BioSample** (TaxID: 1334085): SAMN43395848

Raw Sequencing Data (NCBI SRA)

- **Oxford Nanopore**: SRR30599638
- **PacBio HiFi**: SRR30599641
- **Illumina 150bp PE**: SRR30599640
- **Hi-C 150bp PE**: SRR30599639

Parental Species Reference Data

- ***C. macrocephalus* (Haplotype 1)**: SAMN46907808
- ***C. gariepinus* (Haplotype 2)**: SAMN46730924

Additional Sequencing Data

- **Female *C. macrocephalus***: SAMN42503781
- **Male *C. gariepinus***: SAMN43548335

Figure 1. F1 Hybrid Catfish Genome Card and Global Assembly Metrics.

Code Availability

No custom software was developed for this study. All bioinformatics analyses were performed using publicly available tools with parameters detailed in the Methods section of the main manuscript. Software versions and specific parameter settings are provided throughout the Supplementary Methods.

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Figure 2. GenomeScope 2.0 profiles for parental species and F1 hybrid catfish. Combined analysis showing heterozygosity and genome size estimates based on k-mer sizes $k=21$ and $k=31$. **Bottom-left:** F1 hybrid at $k=21$ showing 10% heterozygosity reflecting genome-wide nucleotide divergence between parental species. **Bottom-right:** F1 hybrid at $k=31$ with genome size 1.8 Gb representing combined subgenomes and hybrid catfish subgenomes separated, lowering heterozygosity to the average of the two pure parental species sub-genomes (0.056% for bighead catfish and 1.56% for North African catfish, displayed in the upper-right and upper-left panels, respectively), resulting in an intermediate value. BUSCO results confirmed assembly completeness and highlight the hybrid's two subgenomes, evidenced by the doubling of genome content. Bighead catfish shows 0.056% heterozygosity, while North African catfish exhibits 1.56%, consistent across sexes and in line with previous studies. Note: Upper panel peaks are not clearly visible due to low Illumina coverage ($<20\times$), resulting in broad peaks rather than distinct bimodal distributions.

(A) IGV Screenshot 1 (Chromosome 03, QV Improvement Before and After Iterative Polishing and Manual Curation)

(B) IGV Screenshot 2 (Gap and Coverage Analysis in fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_02 - False Duplication in Hybrid Assemblies)

Figure 3. Assembly validation and QV improvement through manual curation. (A) Chromosome 03 showing QV improvement after iterative polishing rounds, with clear reduction in k-mer error rates and increased base accuracy. (B) Chromosome 02 demonstrating identification and correction of a false duplication event present in Hifiasm but absent in Flye assembly, supported by coverage analysis and cross-assembly validation. These examples illustrate the critical importance of manual curation in achieving high-quality genome assemblies.

Figure 4. F1 hybrid catfish assembly progress over one year. Timeline showing assembly improvement from January 2024 to November 2024, illustrating the reduction in gap count and improvement in chromosomal continuity through iterative manual curation and polishing rounds. The progress demonstrates the substantial effort required for high-quality hybrid genome assembly.

Figure 5. Hi-C interaction maps for North African catfish subgenome. Individual contact matrices for all 28 pseudochromosomes of the *Clarias gariepinus* haplotype within the F1 hybrid assembly. Each panel represents a single chromosome showing intra-chromosomal Hi-C contacts (dark blue indicating high contact frequency, white indicating no contact). Strong diagonal patterns confirm high assembly contiguity and accurate chromosome-scale scaffolding.

Figure 6. Hi-C interaction maps for bighead catfish subgenome. Individual contact matrices for all 27 pseudo-chromosomes of the *Clarias macrocephalus* haplotype within the F1 hybrid assembly. Each panel displays intra-chromosomal Hi-C contact patterns demonstrating successful chromosome-scale assembly and haplotype resolution. The clear diagonal signals indicate minimal structural errors and high assembly quality.